

Advances in the synthesis of modified NTPs

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Nucleoside triphosphates (NTPs) are building blocks of nucleic acids and play an important role in molecular biology, like PCR and diagnostics, as well as pharmaceutical applications. So far, the golden standard to produce modified NTPs are chemical syntheses. Chemical production routes show limitations due to a low regio- and stereo-selectivity and the need for protection groups. Therefore, they often lead to low yields and are expensive and time consuming. As an alternative, different enzymatic synthesis pathways have been developed. They offer the advantage of high stereo- and regioselectivity which leads to greatly reduced reaction and purification effort as well as often high product yields. While chemical synthesis routes for NTPs have been discussed extensively a comparison to enzymatic methods in terms of yield, production steps and production times is lacking. The aim of this review is to describe the relevance of NTP analogs in a number of applications and to compare described chemical and enzymatic methods for NTP synthesis. AraCTP was chosen as an example to demonstrate advantages and disadvantages of the different approaches.

1. Introduction

Nucleotides are building blocks of nucleic acid (deoxyribonucleic acid, DNA, and ribonucleic acid, RNA) and play a central role in metabolism. Nucleoside triphosphates like adenosine-5'-triphosphate (ATP), guanosine-5'-triphosphate (GTP), cytidine-5'-triphosphate (CTP) and uridine-5'-triphosphate (UTP) are involved in energy metabolism and serve as energy source in many cellular processes like the synthesis of carbohydrates, lipids or amino acids ^[1].

An increasing number of commercial applications for nucleotide triphosphates was observed during the last years. With an increasing availability of DNA and RNA polymerases modified nucleoside triphosphates are becoming important building blocks for the enzymatic synthesis of nucleic acids. With the explosion of sequencing microbial genomes and transcriptomes in the last years nucleic acid sequencing became a main application of nucleoside triphosphate analogs. The applied NTPs are modified with both a fluorescent tag and mainly a reversibly terminating blocking group. By ongoing engineering

of polymerases the sequencing procedure is steadily improved. It correlates with the increasing need for new modifications of modified nucleoside triphosphates ^[2].

The growing need for NTP analogs in a number of applications has driven the development and optimization of chemical and enzymatic production routes with the aim to synthesize modified NTPs with high yield and purity. While chemical methods are described to require protection and deprotection steps and a tedious purification process, for enzymatic methods low yields and high cost were shown to be challenges ^[3]. While available chemical methods have been reviewed intensively, available enzymatic methods have only been shortly summarized. This review will summarize shortly major chemical and enzymatic methods from the last decades.

2. Relevance of modified nucleotides

The analogs of various NTPs nowadays play an important role in molecular biology applications or pharmaceutical industry.

Table 1: Applications of modified nucleotides.

Application	Described NTP modifications
Random PCR for mutagenesis approaches using dNTP analogs	2'-Deoxy-P-nucleoside-5'-Triphosphate (dPTP)
Fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH)	LNA, PNA-nucleotides
Crystallography of nucleic acids	2-seleno-UTP (2Se-UTP)
Chemical modifications of nucleic acid aptamers for therapeutic purposes	Pegaptanib (PEGylated aptamer angiogenesis inhibitor)
Standards for the quantification of drugs	N6-(6-aminohexyl)adenosine, chloro-ATP, bromo-ATP
Antiviral Nucleotides (prodrugs)	sofosbuvir, tenofovir
RNA vaccines	Pseudouridine/-triphosphate, N1-methylpseudouridine/-triphosphate

They are gaining interest as small molecules themselves or as building blocks for oligonucleotides which in turn are applied in different fields. There are mainly two approaches used to add modifications to nucleic acids: I. After the synthesis of nucleic acids modifications are added by chemical methods. II. By using NTP analogs modifications are added to the growing nucleic acid strand. Due to advances in the development of optimized RNA and DNA polymerases a wide range of NTP analogs are nowadays well accepted [4,5]. Even long oligonucleotides can be obtained on a large scale (multi-mg quantity). So far, 2700 nt RNA has been successfully synthesized by Syn5 RNA polymerase [6].

2.1 NTP analogs in molecular biology

A widespread procedure in molecular biology is the random mutagenesis. NTP analogs are applied to achieve high and controllable rates of mutation [7,8]. The nucleotide derivative 2'-deoxy-P-nucleoside-5'-Triphosphate (dPTP) is suitable substrate, which is used instead of TTP for a Taq polymerase based assay [7]. Other nucleotide analogs that were applied for random mutagenesis approaches are dITP [9,10], 8-oxo-GTP [7,11], 2-OH-dATP [12] and BrdUTP [13] (Table 1). Another important application area of NTP analogs is the production of probes for fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH). Directly labeled FISH probes are produced by incorporation of NTP analogs. LNA (locked nucleic acids)- or PNA (peptide nucleic acids)-NTPs were used for FISH [14]. The application of LNA-FISH led to enhanced resolution and sensitivity [15,16].

The application of PNA oligonucleotides resulted in the formation of duplexes with higher stability in contrast to natural homo- or hetero-duplexes [17].

2.2 Application of NTP analogs in crystallographic approaches

As nucleic acids have crucial functions in biological processes they are believed to be very important to understand the cellular mechanisms involved in diverse diseases [18,19]. To gain the precise and detailed information of nucleic acids' biological functions, it is essential to get these compounds and investigate the interaction with their intracellular targets. Modified nucleic acids containing selenium or bromine have been applied to facilitate crystallography of nucleic acids or protein-nucleic acid complexes [20]. As an example, the application of Se-containing nucleic acids was shown to facilitate crystallography in both phasing and crystallization without significant perturbation. Moreover, direct selenium derivatization of nucleic acids has many incomparable advantages over other traditional methods [21].

2.3 Aptamer technologies

Aptamers are short single-stranded DNA or RNA oligonucleotides. They are used as drugs, drug carriers and diagnostic tools [22]. Aptamers are modified to convert them into clinical therapeutics [23,24]. For this purpose, various types of modifications are made, such as modifications on the sugar ring [24] and the locked nucleic acid (LNA) [25,26].

2.4 Pharmaceutical application of NTP analogs

Standards for the quantification of drugs

Endogenous nucleotides and their analogs play a crucial role in multiple cell functions. Hence, the determination of their intracellular levels is of big interest when studying the energy metabolism or other biochemical processes [27]. Furthermore, it helps to understand the mechanism of action of nucleoside drugs [28,29] and the reason for drug resistance [30] or toxic effects [31]. A number of methods have been developed for the quantification of NTP analogs and are based on the use of standards [28]. More recent methods, such as the use of MS-linked approaches, do not rely on standards [32]. However, these methods are very extensive, expensive and require special equipment.

Utilization of nucleotide prodrugs

Nucleoside analogs are effective drugs against cancer or viral infections [33]. In most cases, they have to be phosphorylated *in vivo* in three continuous steps by host cell or viral kinases because they are only active as the equivalent NTP [34]. Often, this activation of the nucleoside analog is insufficient due to the specificity of the host enzymes. Therefore, the use of nucleoside prodrugs is of great interest [35]. Protected NMPs have been used in several approaches to overcome the first activation step *in vivo* (Tan, Chu and Boudinot 1999). Furthermore, methods for the production of NDP or NTP prodrugs have been developed recently [34]. Metabolic reactions such as the deamination of nucleosides or NMPs can be avoided by the application of NDP or NTP prodrugs. Therefore, an increased bioavailability of the drug is observed.

RNA vaccines

The current Corona pandemic drew immense attention to mRNA vaccines. Main modifications applied for improved nucleic acid properties like stability or immune response include pseudouridine or methylpseudouridine [36].

3. Approaches for the chemical synthesis of NTP analogs

So far, the golden standard to produce modified NTPs is the chemical synthesis. Various methods are used depending on the modification of the nucleotide. In the following, four long known methods will be presented briefly. The Yoshikawa method is one of the first methods and still the best-known. The method basically consists of three reactions. First, an unprotected nucleoside precursor is selectively monophosphorylated with the electrophilic phosphorous oxychloride (POCl_3) at the 5'-position of the sugar ring.

A very reactive phosphorodichlorate intermediate is formed and subsequently it reacts with a pyrophosphate to form a cyclic triphosphate. Through hydrolysis the desired nucleoside triphosphate is generated [37,38]. The method is characterized by its simplicity and the fact that in contrast to earlier methods no protection groups are necessary. With this method, it is possible to modify a wide variety of nucleotides [39] but due to the use of a strong electrophilic phosphorous reagent, the method cannot be applied to all nucleosides [40]. In addition, modern analytical techniques have shown that many unwanted by-products are formed by using this method [41].

The Ludwig-Eckstein procedure, a "one-pot, three-steps" method, is the most approved and most-known method for the synthesis of nucleotide derivatives [39]. This synthetic way produces by far less by-products than the Yoshikawa method. The free 5'-hydroxyl group of a protected modified nucleoside precursor reacts with salicyl phosphorochlorite and an activated phosphite intermediate is created. Tris(tetra-n-butylammonium) hydrogen pyrophosphate is added to the intermediate and two nucleophilic substitution reactions result in the formation of a cyclic intermediate which reacts in an iodine-mediated oxidation to the modified nucleotide triphosphate [42]. In comparison to the Yoshikawa method the Ludwig and Eckstein synthesis pathway is a bit longer [39].

A huge amount of modified nucleoside triphosphates has already been synthesized using this approach (e.g. locked nucleic acid NTPs [43–46] and nucleotides bearing unnatural bases) [39,47–49].

Another possibility to chemically phosphorylate nucleosides is the Borch approach, which forms the triphosphate via a very reactive zwitterionic intermediate. The zwitterion is formed by activating the O-benzyl-protected phosphoramidate ester by removing the protecting group. The reactive zwitterion builds with an electrophilic pyrophosphate the nucleoside triphosphate [50]. In contrast to the other methods this approach is reported to have higher yields, less by-products and no problems with strong electrophilic phosphorous reagents.

A method that is completely different from the ones mentioned before is the direct aqueous cross-coupling reaction. For the synthesis of modified nucleotides, halogenated nucleoside triphosphates are utilized [51]. This application was already used to generate dNTPs bearing a number of different functional groups [39].

Several new methods with a number of advantages have been developed. The advantages compared to the older methods are fewer steps, higher yields, no necessary protection or deprotection, sustainability due to the reduced use of toxic solvents and the use of aqueous solutions. The multitude of approaches is well summarized and solution-phase and solid-support syntheses are differentiated [1,3,52].

4. Approaches for the enzymatic synthesis of NTP analogs

Different approaches have been described to produce NTP analogs biologically. Calf thymus kinase extract was used to obtain several sugar-modified pyrimidine and purine NTPs using NMPs as substrates [53]. The authors synthesized dCTP and araCTP as well as both 2'-deoxy-2'-azido-CTP and -UTP in quantitative yields. While they reached 100 % conversion for 2',3'-dideoxy-3'-amino dAMP only 58 % 2',3'-dideoxy-3'-azido dATP and 65 % 2'-deoxy-2'-amino GMP were converted to the respective NTP. Chemically synthesized NDPs were used as substrate for a commercial NDP kinase to synthesize

base-modified NTPs 8-hydroxy-dGTP, 2-hydroxy-dATP [54] and different azole carboxamide dNTPs [40]. Using whole *Erwinia herbicola* cells and a yeast kinase extract sugar-modified NTPs 3'-F-(d)ATP and 3'-F-(d)GTP were produced from the respective nucleosides in a two-pot reaction [55]. Several other reports describe (chemo)enzymatic methods to produce NTPs of known drugs like Ribavirin [56], Carbovir derivatives [57] or 5-fluorinated CTP/UTP variants [58]. NMPs, nucleosides or nucleobases were used as substrates and the biocatalysts were either extracted from human or animal tissues or have been heterologously produced using microorganisms. Our group established a modular one-pot system for the synthesis of NTPs from nucleosides that only consist of heterologously produced and purified nucleoside and nucleotide kinases [59]. We demonstrated the broad applicability of the approach on base- and sugar-modified NTPs (2F-ATP, 5F-CTP, araATP and araCTP).

In a large number of studies enzyme extracts were applied for the production of nucleotides and their analogs. Despite some advantages like easy availability and low production costs crude enzyme extracts generally hampered product purification due to contaminants and the formation of side products. Therefore, an increasing number of approaches made use of purified biocatalysts that are either applied as immobilized or free multi-enzyme cascades (Lopez-Gallego and Schmidt-Dannert 2010). For a three-step process as observed for nucleoside triphosphorylation an *in vitro* approach offers several advantages like a prevention of side products or an easier regulation. The complex cell environment is reduced to highly specific reaction conditions which can be designed as desired by combining the necessary enzymes in a modular system. High yields and simplified product purification protocols were accomplished. Furthermore, it offers the possibility to produce toxic compounds [60]. Cofactor regeneration systems can easily be included to reduce expensive substrates and to shift reaction equilibrium towards the product [59,61].

Figure 1: Different synthesis routes for AraCTP. Chemical methods are shown on the left and enzymatic methods on the right. *) isolated yield (after purification). **) formation of several products (NTP yield is lower). ***) total yield calculated from yields of single stages.

5. Comparison of chemical and biological synthesis routes for NTP analogs

In the synthesis of natural and modified NTPs, chemical and biological procedures represent fundamentally different approaches. In this chapter, the key parameters of both synthesis routes will be compared on the basis of the modified NTP arabinosylcytosine triphosphate (araCTP). Several chemical and biological synthesis routes have been published for araCTP and are summarized in **Figure 1**.

5.1 Chemical approaches for AraCTP synthesis

In 1964, Cardeilhac and Cohen published the first experiments to synthesize araCTP both chemically and biologically in two-pot reactions [62]. For the chemical NMP synthesis, they applied the method by Weiss et al. which gave good results for cytidine as substrate (30 % CMP yield) [63]. For that, the unprotected nucleoside was incubated in polyphosphoric acid for 45 min at 60°C.

In case of araC very low NMP yields of 6 % were achieved because of the large degree of deamination and cleavage of the glycosidic bond which lead to the formation of the side products uracil, cytosine, araU as well as 3'-phosphorylated araC. 5'-AraCMP was purified in three steps before it was used as substrate for the NTP synthesis via a carbodiimide method [64].

By using this general procedure for NTP synthesis based on dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) and orthophosphoric acid yields of 10 % araCTP were reported (after purification presumably) without providing any further details.

The number of reaction steps and use of solvents can be assumed similar as in a comparable NTP analog synthesis [65]. There, in eight steps in over 48 h 5F-UTP was produced from the respective NMP. Several solvents like tributylamine, pyridine and ether were applied. For Cardheilac and Cohen, the combined synthesis routes for araCMP and araCTP resulted in a total araCTP yield of less than 1 %.

In a patent application from 2009 Peyrottes et al. describe two five-step (nine stage) approaches for araCTP synthesis from araC which only differ in the last two steps (WO 2009115694 A1, FR 2927901 A1). Cumulated yields of 42 and 4.5 %, respectively, are reached in a total working time of two or three days. Initially, the nucleoside substrate is coupled to bifunctionalized PEG and monophosphorylated using triethyl phosphate and POCl₃. Two more phosphates are added using tributylammonium pyrophosphate before araCTP is cleaved of the polymeric support and lyophilized. Several solvents like dichloromethane, DMF and methanol are applied.

The second production variant is one day faster at the expense of product yield.

In 2010, Kusuhara et al. published a simple one-pot approach in which 75 % araC is converted to a mixture of 5'-, 3'- and 2'-araCTP. For that, the nucleoside is incubated with cyclic triphosphate in a ratio of 1:10 for 25 days at 25°C and pH 12. While the actual 5'-NTP yield is not known, it is worth mentioning that this method can only be applied to a limited number of nucleoside substrates. For ribonucleosides only 2'- and 3'- phosphorylation occurs while the approach cannot be used for deoxyribonucleosides at all.

While the previously described methods use araC as substrate another chemical approach by Wu et al. starts from the base-protected nucleoside [50]. A highly reactive pyrrolidinium phosphoramidate zwitterion intermediate is coupled with tris(tetra-n-butylammonium) hydrogen phosphate. In nine stages over two days an isolated yield of 55 % is reached using several solvents like pyridine, dichloromethane and DMF. The NTP synthesis procedure worked well for thymidine as substrate but required several adaptations to be useful for araCTP synthesis. In order to increase substrate solubility THF was replaced with DMF as solvent and the palladium catalyst had to be used on alumina instead of activated carbon. Additionally, water had to be added to enable the catalyst's removal.

5.2 Biological approaches for AraCTP synthesis

Next to their chemical approach, in the same mentioned publication Cardeilhac and Cohen presented an enzymatic alternative for the synthesis of araCTP in order to produce the isotopic variant araCTP-H3. In a first step they synthesized araCMP from araC (140 mM) by using wheat shoot extract and *p*-nitrophenylphosphate (NPP, 225 mM) as phosphate donor based on a previously published method [66]. After incubation for 6 h at 30°C a constant concentration of 100 mM NPP was reached which indicates a maximal araCMP yield of 89 %.

This value could be improved by repeated removal of the side product *p*-nitrophenol and addition of enzyme and NPP. After purification they employed purified *E. coli* CMP kinase and pyruvate kinase to

phosphorylate araCMP-H3 in <1 mM scale. According to the reported similarity to their araCDP synthesis the reaction apparently did not take more than a few hours. It was stopped when more than 69 % of the NMP substrate were converted but the actual NTP yield was not stated. Therefore, the resulting total yield after five stages cannot exceed 61 %. Our group reached 100 % araCTP yield after 4 h incubation at 37°C using a one-pot mixture of three commercial nucleoside, NMP and NDP kinases, an ATP regeneration system and 1 mM araC as substrate [59]. Another biological one-pot route for araCTP synthesis reported by Imazawa et al. (1979) employed the NMP as starting compound. A partially purified kinase-extract from calf-thymus containing different NMP kinases and NDP kinase as well as an ATP regeneration system was used to convert araCMP to araCTP in 0.5 μmol (4 mM) scale. 100 % conversion was reached within 30 min at 37°C. Whole *S. cerevisiae* cells were used by Titovich et al. to generate NDPs and NTPs from a number of NMPs [67]. Incubation of 40 mM araCMP in potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7), 15 mM MgCl₂, 2 % glucose and 10 % dried yeast cells for 2-7 h at 20-28°C resulted in the formation of 78 % araCDP plus araCTP.

Except for Cardeilhac & Cohen's route all biological araCTP synthesis approaches are one-pot methods while only our group's method uses the nucleoside araC as substrate. Additionally, regarding time and effort Titovich's application of whole yeast cells as well as our use of commercial enzymes is favorable over the self-expressed or purified catalysts in Cardeilhac's and Imazawa's approaches. Additionally, with respect to sustainability and scalability calf-thymus is not a suitable source for biocatalysts. Due to the natural enzyme's promiscuity the application of yeast cells and *E. coli* or animal extracts very likely is limited to certain nucleoside substrates while the modular approach using purified enzymes offers the possibility to generate a broad range of products.

In comparison, the chemical synthesis routes appear much more laborious.

Three out of four procedures require nine to 12 stages and result in maximal 55 % yield. However, purification steps and losses are usually included. Kusuhara's one-step approach is significantly simpler than the others but with 25 days also dramatically slower. Furthermore, since three products are formed with unknown ratios subsequent purification steps are necessary. With respect to sustainability and safety the use of solvents and other critical reagents is another disadvantage of the chemical methods.

At the same time, it remains to be investigated whether the high yields and simplicity of the biological methods can make up for the usually high costs connected to the use of biocatalysts.

6. Conclusion

NTP analogs are used in a large and growing number of applications. On one hand, they are applied as building blocks for the synthesis of modified nucleic acids or in sequencing approaches. On the other hand, they are active as monomers can be used as antiviral drugs. Due to an increasing number of applications for NTP analogs steadily new chemical and enzymatic methods are developed to overcome recent drawbacks like sustainability or a missing transferability to a wide variety of NTP analogs. Large improvements were observed during the last few years, however, there is still a need for further optimization to transfer especially sustainable chemical methods or enzymatic processes to industrial scale.

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